

Donor Properties of Pyridine Carboxylic Acids : Mixed Ligand Zinc(II) Complexes

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Complexes of Zn(II), [Zn(bipy/phen/dmephen)(dpc/CollH)] with dipicolinic (dpcH₂) and heterocyclic bases like 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2,9-dimethylphenanthroline (dmephen) have been prepared and characterised. Probable structures are discussed on the basis of solubility and ir spectra of the complexes and VSEPR theory.

IN continuation of our previous work on pyridine carboxylic acid complexes with chromium^{1,2}, a few mixed ligand zinc(II) complexes have been isolated and characterised, the ligands used being pyridine di- and tricarboxylic acids and heterocyclic bases like bipyridyl, phenanthroline and substituted phenanthroline.

Experimental

Dipicolinic and collidinic acids were prepared by literature methods³⁻⁵. Zn(II)acetate dihydrate (Sarabhai M Chemicals, A.R.) was used without further purification.

Preparation of the complexes :

Equimolar amounts of aqueous zinc(II)acetate dihydrate and aqueous alcoholic solution of bipyridyl were mixed. Excess (1.5 moles) hot aqueous solution of dipicolinic acid was added to the mixture and heated on steam bath for a short period when white precipitate of the complex, [Zn(dipy)(dpc)], was formed. The product was filtered and washed repeatedly with boiling water until it was free from excess dipicolinic acid. The compound was dried in air.

Other complexes of this series were obtained by adopting the above procedure.

Physical measurements :

Zinc was estimated by EDTA titration. Nitrogen was estimated by semi-micro Dumas's technique and carbon, hydrogen values were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow (results in Table 1). The ir spectra were scanned on Beckman infracord in KBr (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The chemistry of bivalent pentacoordinated zinc complexes has been investigated by many workers⁶⁻¹⁰. Zinc(II) ion has 3d¹⁰ configuration and usually attains tetrahedral geometry using 4sp³ hybridisation but the possibility of forming pentacoordination (4sp³d) and hexacoordination (4sp³d²) cannot be ruled out.

Ciampolini and Nardi¹¹ have pointed out that pentacoordinated complexes are formed with ligands having strong σ-bonding ability and little π-bonding tendency. The ligand must be bulky and a polydentate one so that crowding around the metal ion should prevent the attainment of an octahedral

TABLE I—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				m.p. °C
			Metals	Nitrogen	Carbon	Hydrogen	
1.	[Zn(phen)(dpc)]	White	16.40 (15.83)	9.90 (10.23)	54.70 (55.95)	2.55 (2.69)	280
2.	[Zn(dipy)(dpc)]	White	17.26 (18.94)	10.56 (10.89)	51.60 (52.91)	2.72 (2.84)	280
3.	[Zn(dmephen)(dpc)]	White	14.50 (14.26)	9.45 (9.60)	58.10 (58.26)	3.26 (3.42)	280
4.	[Zn(phen)(collH)]	White	15.00 (13.84)	8.90 (9.30)	51.35 (53.15)	2.30 (2.41)	280
5.	[Zn(bipy)(collH)]	White	15.50 (14.61)	9.50 (9.82)	49.37 (50.52)	2.35 (2.55)	280
6.	[Zn(dmephen)(collH)]	White	12.85 (13.03)	8.60 (8.74)	55.08 (55.05)	3.23 (3.12)	280

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TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES

Ligand/Complex	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\Delta_{C=O}$	ν_{C-O}	$\nu_{bipy/phen}$
1. dpcH ₂	1690	—	1300	—
2. [Zn(phen)(dpc)]	1630	60	1375 ^a	730 s, 1150 s, 1430 m
3. [Zn(dipy)(dpc)]	1610	80	1375	745 s, 760 s, 1150 m, 1460 s
4. [Zn(dmephen)(dpc)]	1635	55	1370	—
5. collH ₂	1730	—	1270	—
6. [Zn(phen)(collH)]	1630 ^a	100	1350 ^a	730 s, 1150 s, 1440 m
7. [Zn(bipy)(collH)]	1615 ^a	115	1350	730 s, 1150 s, 1425 s
8. [Zn(dmephen)(collH)]	1650	80	1350	—

a=mean value, s=sharp and m=medium.

configuration. With this in mind we have used strong field polydentate (tridentate) bulky ligands like dipicolinic and collidinic acids in isolating pentacoordinated bivalent zinc complexes.

According to VSEPR theory^{1,2}, for elements with d¹⁰ configuration trigonal bipyramidal structure is favoured in strongly covalent complexes while square pyramidal geometry is favoured by ionic bonding.

All the complexes are white, crystalline and have high m.p. The elemental analysis indicates the presence of [MN₃O₂] chromophoric group in them. The complexes are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents and water and this did not permit the measurement of conductivity or determination of molecular weight. The insolubility of the complexes indicates polymerisation. X-ray crystallographic studies of Ca(dpc).3H₂O¹³ and Sr(dpc).4H₂O¹⁴, respectively supports this idea where the former salt forms a dimer and the latter one forms a continuous ribbon type structure consisting of alternately oriented dipicolinate ion bonded to Sr²⁺ ion. Further, X-ray structural evaluation of Zn(pic)₂.4H₂O¹⁵ and Zn(nic)₂.4H₂O¹⁶ (pic=picolinate ion and nic=nicotinate ion) complexes dictates the octahedral disposition of donor atoms i.e., the Zn²⁺ ion is surrounded by two nitrogen atoms and four oxygen atoms of four water molecules. The above structural studies in conjunction with the poor solubility of zinc(II) complexes described in this communication in polar and non-polar solvents suggest the following dimeric (hexacoordinated) structure.

Zn(II) ion being of d¹⁰ configuration does not show d-d transition and electronic spectra do not furnish any information about the stereochemistry of

the complexes. The structural information of the complexes has, therefore, been derived from their ir spectral measurements. The ir spectral bands of diagnostic value, of ligands as well as of the complexes are recorded in Table 2. The values indicate that for all the complexes the symmetric vibration of carbonyl group, $\nu_{C=O}$, are shifted to higher wave numbers while the antisymmetric stretch, ν_{C-O} , gets shifted to lower wave numbers compared to corresponding ligands. The position of antisymmetric stretch, $\nu_{C=O}$, in all these complexes clearly indicates that the metal ion forms a covalent bond to the carbonyl oxygen of the pyridine carboxylic acids. Further, appearance of new characteristic ir bands at around 730, 1150 and 1425-1460 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of coordinated bipyridyl and phenanthroline which are slightly deviated from the positions indicated by Dutta^{17,18}. It is not surprising that the metal-oxygen as well as the metal-nitrogen bond order change their positions with the degree of covalency¹⁹⁻²¹.

The ir spectral study of all the complexes suggests that the bonding should be covalent. Thus, following VSEPR theory it may be suggested that the complexes, if pentacoordinated, should attain trigonal bipyramidal geometry. However, the strong tendency to dimerise probably changes the compound to a hexacoordinated complex.

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